

St. John Chrysostom, Homilies On the Incomprehensible Nature of God

also known as "On the Incomprehensibility of the Divine Nature"

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Entry tags: Christianity, Arianism, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Byzantine, Greek, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Greek Orthodox, Text, Christian Theology, Christian Traditions, Orthodox Christianity, Apologetics, Language, Byzantine text

An important place among John's discourses are the five sermons on God's incomprehensibility. They form a unity, which the editors have incorporated into a series of discourses which Chrysostom delivered against the Anomoeans. The Anomoeans was a religious group that represented an extreme form of Arianism. Arius and his followers believed that the essential difference between God and Christ was that God had always existed, while Christ was created by God. The Anomoeans distorted the Nicene Creed formulation that the "Son of God, the only begotten of the Father" meant that the Father is believed to be unbegotten and the Son being begotten made God. Therefore, the Father and the Son are unlike (ἀνόμοιου). The founder of the Anomoeans, Aëtius of Antioch, held that God and Christ could not be alike. Since ingenerateness is a crucial part of the essence of God, Christ could not be like God because he lacked this essential quality. Another principal belief of the Anomoeans was the ingenerateness (ἀγεννησία) of God the Father. Being ingenerated, the Father could never come into contact or communicate His nature to generated beings. Therefore, the Son is generated (γεννητός), created by the power of the Ingenerated Father. The homilies Against the Anomoeans (twelve in number) fall into two series both in theme as well as in time and place. The setting was unique: not only were the Anomoeans present among his flock to listen to John, but they had even challenged him. This was a fine opportunity both to refute the errors of the Anomoeans and to instruct his creed in the tenets of the true faith. Chrysostom, hence, could work for the conversion of the Anomoeans, and, at the same time, he could protect his own flock. The first five sermons were delivered in Antioch, in the autumn of 386, that is, the year in which Chrysostom had been ordained as a presbyter. The first sermon was delivered presumably at the end of August, while the rest during November and December of the same year. Although the theme of the sermons is strictly doctrinal, there is a number of moral exhortations, so dear to Chrysostom. For this reason, John also introduces the issue of prayer in these five sermons, particularly towards the end of each speech. In these five sermons Chrysostom mainly deals with a key point of the Anomean teaching, as posited by Eunomius: the epistemological problem. Following Aristotle, the Eunomius and his followers admitted that the human intellectual capacity is unlimited and able to conceive both the nature of the world and the actions of God. Thus, what God knows about himself, can be also known by humans. The Orthodox theologians, hence, diagnosed two tendencies in the Anomean teaching, which give rise to two problems: 1) the tendency to declare man epistemologically self-sufficient, since he is able to grasp with his intellect everything, therefore he does not need God; 2) the tendency to diminish the greatness of God, since they persist in the abusive attempt to make God an object of curiosity and intellectual inquiry, as an object accessible to the human intellect. So, according to Chrysostom, God is transcendent and inconceivable. As the sole principle, cause and source of all beings and all goods, God acts through and with his Word (Logos). It is therefore impossible for human beings to conceive the inconceivable God. Being finite with limited intellectual capabilities and moving within the epistemological limits that God has provided to, human beings cannot reach the full understanding of the divine mystery. However, Chrysostom does not promote agnosticism. On the contrary, God gave man the possibility of partial knowledge. This is a natural result of His goodness, that is, that he descends into the world and allows himself to be known. God reveals Himself, but what He reveals is not His essence, but His divine energies. For this reason, the human intellect can never comprehend God's essence, but only His will and His energies. Such revelation comes through faith. It does not need logical constructions, only auxiliary, interpretive ones. Regarding the following seven sermons, the 6th sermon is a break in the sequence of Chrysostom's attack against the Anomoeans. John has proved that God's nature is incomprehensible to every creature and has introduced the second part of his argument, the "glory of the only begotten," the con substantiality of the Son with the Father. Therefore, the theme in sermons 7-12 that the Son is one in substance with the Father. So, in the remaining sermons Chrysostom sets to complete his discussion of the Son's co-substantiality. Hence, sermons 7 and 8 have the same theme with sermons 9 and 10, since they all stress the glory of the only begotten and His equality in power with the Father. So the twelve homilies against the Anomoeans treat of two themes, the incomprehensibility of God (sermons 1-5) and the

consubstantiality of Christ with the Father (sermons 7-12); they fall into two series separated by time and place: sermons 1-5 were delivered at Antioch in the years 386-87; sermons 11 and 12 belong to 398 and were preached in Constantinople.

Date Range: 347 CE - 407 CE

Region: Byzantine Antioch

Region tags: Byzantium, Asia Minor, Eastern Mediterranean

Antioch, the city where John Chrysostom preached his sermons.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Translated by Paul Harkins, *On the Incomprehensible Nature of God*, John Chrysostom, The Catholic University of America Press 2010
- Source 1: *Sur l'incompréhensibilité de Dieu : Homélie I-V*, Translated by Robert Flacelière & Jean Daniélou, Paris, CERF, Sources chrétiennes, 2000
- Source 1: *De l'incompréhensibilité de Dieu*, Jean Chrysostome, Translated by Pierre Marenchaux, Rivages, Paris 2000
- Source 2: *Homelies sur l'incompréhensibilité de Dieu*, Jean Chrysostome, Translated by Jean-Yves Leloup, Albin Michel, Paris 1993

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://bradkelly.wordpress.com/tag/john-chrysostom/>
- Source 1 Description: John Chrysostom On the Incomprehensible Nature of God Sermon 10
- Source 1 URL: <https://nominis.cef.fr/contenus/saint/5401/Saint-Jean-Chrysostome.html>
- Source 1 Description: Saint Jean Chrysostome Évêque de Constantinople, Docteur de l'Église
- Source 1 URL: <https://orthochristian.com/127870.html>
- Source 1 Description: ST. JOHN CHRYSOSTOM ON THE FAMILY AND THE UPBRINGING OF CHILDREN A mother's notes
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Saint-John-Chrysostom>
- Source 1 Description: St. John Chrysostom archbishop of Constantinople
- Source 2 URL: <https://christianhistoryinstitute.org/magazine/article/john-chrysostom-timeline>
- Source 2 Description: Christian History Timeline: John Chrysostom

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.goldenmouth.org/treatises/on-the-incomprehensibility-of-God>
- Source 1 Description: ON THE INCOMPREHENSIBILITY OF GOD
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/onincomprehensib0072john/page/n7/mode/2up>
- Source 2 Description: On the incomprehensible nature of God by John Chrysostom

- Source 3 URL: <https://archive.org/details/surlgalitdupreet0396john>
- Source 3 Description: Sur l'égalité du Père et du fils : contre les anoméens homélie VII-XII by John Chrysostom
- Source 1 URL: https://www.academia.edu/6448870/Chrysostomica_A_Bibliography_of_Scholarship_on_John_Chrysostom_and_Attribute
- Source 1 Description: Chrysostomica: A Bibliography of Scholarship on John Chrysostom and Attributed Writings
- Source 2 URL: https://www.academia.edu/6448894/Modern_editions_and_translations_of_Chrysostoms_works
- Source 2 Description: Modern editions and translations of Chrysostom's works

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

- Inked
 - with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Other textile: Parchment

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

- No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

- No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

- No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: The text, however, was translated in Syriac, Armenian and the old Russian language.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: Chrysostom's "On the Incomprehensible Nature of God" is in fact a series of non-continuous homilies, which refute the teaching of the followers of Eunomius and of the Anomians in general, who claimed to know the essence of God. The first five homilies are dated between the years 386 and 387.

With the generic title "Against the Anomeans", Migne's *Patrologia Graeca* considers seven independent homilies, preached between 386 and 387, as an addition to the "On the Incomprehensible Nature of God".

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: Not exactly. John, however, in his 6th sermon speaks of another city, the city of God. Recounting the deeds of Philogonius, John says that he left this Church here, on earth, and have become a citizen in the Church of the firstborn who are enrolled in heaven, that he left the earthly festivals and entered into the festal gathering of the angels. For up in heaven there is a city, there is a Church, there is a festival.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: Since God became man, Chrysostom describes (necessarily, so to speak) Christ's incarnate presence in the world in anthropomorphic terms.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarh (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: In his 3d sermon John describes God as the ineffable, who is beyond human intelligence, invisible, incomprehensible, who transcends the power of mortal words. He is furthermore inscrutable to the angels, unseen by the Seraphim, inconceivable to the Cherubim, invisible to the principalities, to the powers, and to the virtues, in fact, to all creatures without qualification.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Notes: Interestingly, in his 7th sermon John rebukes his heretic opponents by posing a series of questions, asking them if God is afraid, if He hesitates and shrinks back, if He feels pain. According to John, if the heretics answer that God does, stay away from them and make them stand at the devil's side, or even deeper in hell than the devil. For even Satan will not dare to say this. But if they (i.e. the heretics) say that none of these feelings is worthy of God, then tell them that neither does Christ pray as God.

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Notes: According to John, God is unapproachable not only for men but also for the powers above. God, moreover, is incomprehensible not only to the Cherubim and Seraphim but also to the Principalities and the Powers and to any other created power. However, in his 3d sermon John states that through communal prayer, one may communicate with God. In the church there is a large throng of spiritual fathers; with one accord, a cry is sent up to God. When one calls upon the Lord by himself, he does not listen to him in the same way as when one invokes him along with his brothers. In the church hence one has something more: the oneness of mind, the unison of voices, the common bond of love, the prayers of the priests.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: In his 1st and 3d sermons John provides rather detailed descriptions of the Seraphims and the Cherubims, i.e. the orders of the angels.

Reference: de Wet, Chris . "Angels in John Chrysostom's Anthropology: Asceticism, Angelomorphism, and Human Bodily Composition in Flux". *Journal of Early Christian History* 10, no. 1 (2020): 21-36. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/2222582X.2020.1854048>.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: Demons

Notes: John, in his 4th sermon, quotes St. Paul regarding the Principalities and Powers and the rulers of this world of darkness of the present age, i.e. orders of demons.

Reference: Lynn Miller, Samantha. No Sympathy for the Devil: The Significance of Demons in John Chrysostom's Soteriology. Milwaukee, Wisconsin: Marquette University, 2016.
https://epublications.marquette.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1625&context=dissertations_mu.

Reference: Lynn Miller, Samantha. Chrysostom's Devil: Demons, the Will, and Virtue in Patristic Soteriology. New Explorations in Theology. Downers Grove, Illinois: IVP Academic, 2020.

Reference: Kalleres, Danya. "The Devil Is in the Ritual". In *City of Demons*, 51-86. Oakland, CA: University of California Press, 2014. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1525/california/9780520276475.003.0002>.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– No

- ↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

- ↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: According to John, God searches the hearts and minds and he knows the thoughts of men

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: John, nevertheless, in his 8th sermon attempts to prove that God is Lord and can mete out punishment or honor and he exhorts his audience to listen to what the Lord himself said when he spoke these words: "When the Son of Man will come in the glory of his Father, he will set the sheep at his right hand and the goats on the left. And he will say to those on his right hand, 'Come, blessed of my Father, take possession of the kingdom prepared for you from the foundation of the world. For I was hungry, and you gave me food; I was thirsty, and you gave me drink.' Then he will say to those on his left hand, 'Depart from me, you cursed, into the fire which was prepared for the devil and his angels. For I was hungry, and you gave me no food; I was thirsty, and you gave me no drink; I was a stranger, and you did not take me in.' " This, according to John, is his perfect judgment and the way he gives both honor and punishment. He can award crowns and he can visit with vengeance. Some he leads into the kingdom and others he sends down into Gehenna.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In his 6th sermon, John speaks about the state of the after life, depicting, so to speak, a state where all troubles have been taken away, where there would be no diseases, no sufferings, no grounds for sinning; and where coldhearted words like "mine" and "yours" shall no longer exist to bring every dread evil into the lives of the people, causing thus countless conflicts.

Reference: Reuling, Hanneke. "Beyond Paradise. John Chrysostom Preaching on the Primordial Ordeal". In *After Eden. Church Fathers and Rabbis on Genesis 3:16-21*, 115–57. Jewish and Christian Perspectives Series. Leiden: Brill, 2006. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789047417019_005.

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

- No
- ↳ At specified time in future
 - No
- ↳ At unspecified time in near future
 - No
- ↳ At unspecified time in distant future
 - Yes
- ↳ At some other time [specify]
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: None, according to the text.
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive
 - Yes
 - ↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive
 - No

- ↳ All members of the sample region will survive
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other survival condition [specify]
 - Specify: None, according to the text.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Reference: Sherwin, Michael. "Friendship with God and the Transformation of Patronage in the Thought of John Chrysostom". *New Blackfriars* 85 (2004): 387-98. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1111/j.1741-2005.2004.00040.x>.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Reference: Walker, Becky. *Almsgiving as the Essential Virtue. A Study of the Homilies of John Chrysostom. Vigiliae Christianae, Supplements*. Leiden: Brill, 2024.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

- Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

- No

↳ Courage (generic)

- No

Notes: Only in a metaphorical manner, for the "battle" against heretic teachings.

Reference: Christou, Theodore. "Raising an Athlete for Christ: Saint John Chrysostom and Education in Byzantium". *Akropolis: Journal of Hellenic Studies* 2 (2018): 105-18.

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

- Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

- Yes

Notes: Surprisingly, John is very concerned regarding the tolerance and the spirit of forgiveness towards heretics. He exhorts his audience to pray and forgive the heretics and treat them as

sick.

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Reference: Cassady, Joel . St. John Chrysostom and His Message of Social Justice Today. Saint John's University: Collegeville, Minnesota, 2010.

https://www.academia.edu/98875019/St_John_Chrysostom_and_His_Message_of_Social_Justice_Today.

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Reference: Jones, A.H.M.. "St. John Chrysostom's Parentage and Education". The Harvard Theological Review 46, no. 3 (1953): 171-73. <https://doi.org/>

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0017816000022616>.

Reference: Widok, Norbert . "Christian Family as Domestic Church in the Writings of St. John Chrysostom". Studia Ceranea 3 (2013): 167-75. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.18778/2084-140X.03.12>.

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Field doesn't know

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Field doesn't know

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Field doesn't know

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Notes: John states that if someone wishes the privilege of the first place and the highest honor, then he should seek the place which is last, he should seek to be less worthy, more humble, less important than all, and rank himself below the others. This is the virtue which gives this honor, according to John. After all, in his 10th sermon John uses Jesus Christ as the perfect example of humility.

Reference: Szram, Mariusz . "Can Humility Exist Without Poverty? A Response by Cappadocian Fathers and John Chrysostom". *Vox Patrum* 62 (2014): 505-10.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.31743/vp.3599>.

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Notes: Concerning gratitude/thankfulness, John praises the power of common prayer, i.e. the prayer that takes place during mass.

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

Reference: Leyerle, Blake . "John Chrysostom and the Strategic Use of Fear". In *Social Control in Late Antiquity. The Violence of Small Worlds*, 173-87. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 2020. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108783491.013>.

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Field doesn't know

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Field doesn't know

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Almsgiving, love. More particularly, love is the beginning and the end of every virtue. through the grace and loving-kindness of our Lord Jesus Christ

Reference: Sitzler, Silke . "Identity: The Indigent and the Wealthy in the Homilies of John Chrysostom". *Vigiliae Christianae* 63, no. 5 (2009): 468-79.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/157007209X413821>.

Reference: Leyerle, Blake. "John Chrysostom on Almsgiving and the Use of Money". *The Harvard Theological Review* 87, no. 1 (1994): 29-47.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/S001781600003162X>.

Reference: Mayer, Wendy. "Poverty and Generosity Towards the Poor in the Time of John Chrysostom". In *Wealth and Poverty in Early Church and Society*, 140-58. *Holy Cross Studies in Patristic Theology and History*. Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Publishing Group, 2008.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: In fact, there is a hint regarding celibacy, which points to the episcopal celibacy. The problem of priestly and episcopal celibacy is a complicated one. What . Clerical celibacy dates back to the earliest days of the Church as a matter of rule. As for apostolic origin (even allowing for some uncertainty as to the precise meaning of "bishop"), it seems settled by Paul in I Tm 3.2, where he says: "A bishop must be irreproachable, married only once . . ." and in Ti 1.6, here he says the same thing for presbyters, adding that they must be the father of children who are believers. Paul also says that a deacon should be the husband of one wife (I Tm 3.12). In patristic times, canon 23 of the Spanish Council of Elvira in 295-303 imposed celibacy on the three higher orders of the clergy, but the restriction was far from universal, especially in the East and for those who were married before ordination.

Reference: Cochini, Christian . *Origines Apostoliques Du Célibat Sacerdotal*. Paris-Namur: Lethielleux et Culture et Vérité, 1981.

Reference: Balducelli, Roger . "The Apostolic Origins of Clerical Continence: A Critical Appraisal of a New Book". *Theological Studies* 43, no. 4 (1982): 693-705.
<https://doi.org/https://ddoi.org/10.1177/004056398204300406>.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: John in fact exhorts his flock to bid everything farewell during the days of the Lent. On the contrary, he advises to begin to observe the feast and stay away from any sort of business of the law courts, of affairs of the City Council and any sort of daily affairs together with their contracts and business deals.

Reference: Meawad, Stephen . "Fasting Reconsidered: St. John Chrysostom and Modern Science on Fasting", 2016.

https://www.academia.edu/38520164/Fasting_Reconsidered_St_John_Chrysostom_and_Modern_Science_on_Fasting.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: In a way, yes. John draws a sharp contrast between the care of the self (or the external appearance) and the care of the soul. He points that people buy new shoes, prepare a more sumptuous table and, generally, they think of many means to provide for themselves in every way. They overlook nothing which will brighten their appearance and make them look stylish and smart. However, they take no account of their soul. It is neglected, clothed in shoddy garments, unwashed, wasted with hunger, and people let it stay uncleansed. "Will you bring here to church your stylish body but overlook your soul, which is half clad and filled with disgrace?", he asks, pointing that people only see the body, and it does them no harm no matter how someone has neglected it. But the Lord sees our soul and he inflicts the greatest punishment on it since, we have been careless and negligent about it.

Reference: Rylaarsdam, David . *John Chrysostom on Divine Pedagogy : The Coherence of His Theology and Preaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014.

Reference: Allen Krupp, Robert . *Shepherding the Flock of God : The Pastoral Theology of John Chrysostom*. New York: P. Lang, 1991.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: John in fact complains about the limited number of his congregation. He says that, due to the chariot races, many of the congregation are missing, therefore the assembly is fewer. He compares himself with a farmer who sees his crop in full bloom and is ready for harvest, and he makes little account of the fact that the leaves are falling. Since, John concludes, a small part of his congregation is present as his harvest, neither he feels such great distress because he sees that the fallen leaves are being swept away, and he does not grieve for the laxity of those who are not present, but still the earnestness of the loving assembly of those who are present consoles him in the pain he feels for those who are absent. He finally states that sometimes those absentees do attend the services. But, even then, they are not really present. Their bodies are there, but their minds are wandering far and wide. Moreover, John exhorts his audience, in his 11th sermon, not to take such poor care of themselves, but to prefer the time they spend in the church to any occupation and concern. He, then asks his audience what profit do they gain which can outweigh the loss they bring on themselves and their whole household when they stay away from the religious service.

Reference: Lugaresi, Leonardo . "Rhetoric Against the Theatre and Theatre by Means of Rhetoric in John Chrysostom". In *Rhetorical Strategies in Late Antique Literature Images, Metatexts and Interpretation*, 117–48. Mnemosyne, Supplements, Late Antique Literature. Leiden: Brill, 2017. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004340114_009.

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Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: Only in a metaphorical manner. John opens his 8th sermon stating that his congregation has returned from war, from a war and battle with the heretics. Their weapons were stained with blood, the sword of John's discourse was red with gore. They did not (John and his audience) strike down their bodies but they did destroy their arguments and every proud pretension which raises itself against the knowledge of God. For such is the kind of battle (i.e. battle for the true faith against the heretics), according to John, and, therefore, such is the nature of the weapons (i.e. his discourse)

Reference: Huovinen, Harri . "Martial Imagery and Church Membership in the Catechetical Rhetoric of John Chrysostom". *Phronema* 37, no. 1 (2022): 99-118.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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